

RESPONSE PAPER

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FIRST NAME: RATIB

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author used MSWord 2016 on Windows

ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK PERIOD ONE (1) (CHAPTER 1-5)

1) INTRODUCTION

This is a response paper to ACA-401D course pack meant to equip Euclid University PhD students with knowledge and skills in international academic writing. Only chapters 1-5 of this course pack has been discussed in this write-up. The selected concepts discussed in this response paper include essentials of essay writing, plagiarism and its consequences in academia, literature review, rules of thumb for writing academic papers, and English language writing styles.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Academic essays are evidence-based. They are expected to answer specific questions, and or argue for or against a concept, theory or a relevant issue. Several steps are followed when writing essays. Though not sequential, the starting point depend on the writer's experience. They include:

- 1) Starting to write as early as possible, by thorough task analysis and defining the questions to answer, constructing an initial plan that acts as a roadmap.
- 2) Reviewing literature in order to get familiar with the topic and have an in-depth knowledge to provide the evidence base to argue for and against the question or issue in question, and develop relevant questions to answer.
- 3) Synthesizing and organizing ideas to provide logical answers to the chosen essay questions.

- 4) Drafting and re-drafting the essay until a fair copy is generated by ensuring the write-up is well structured to include various sections such as an introduction, essay body and conclusion.
- 5) Providing relevant evidence by referencing sources of information in order to avoid plagiarism.
- 6) Editing the write-up to refine its content and make it plausible for its intended purpose and convincing to readers (EUCLID 2019)

It is expected that by following the above steps, a sound, and evidence-based academic essays that meet international academic standards can be written by different authors. In my own opinion, these are essential strategies for writing a sound academic essay and have been well-articulated by authors of Euclid University's course materials for the module "International Academic Writing."

3) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism has been described as an academic dishonesty and unethical behavior practiced by authors/writers who either intentionally or unintentionally fail to give credit to sources of information from which they derived the ideas for arguing for or against a concept, theory, or answers to specific research questions (EUCLID 2019, 5). In the course pack, this chapter teaches Ph.D. students of Euclid University to avoid plagiarism by citing the sources of information they use to inform their academic essay write-ups as described below.

To avoid plagiarism and preserve the tradition of unique knowledge generation that resulted into global civilization, at Euclid University students are expected to use in-text citations and provide a list references. In-text citation means including information derived from the original source into one's academic essay by either direct quotation or paraphrasing the statements followed by inclusion of the author's names and the page number from which the information was extracted. Specific formats have been prescribed for referencing different sources of information such as books, research articles, websites etc. Two referencing styles have been recommended for use by Euclid University students. These are footnote referencing and the inclusion of the references in a separate page at the end of the document (EUCLID 2019, 5–13).

Although comprehensive information has been provided in this chapter on the importance of avoiding plagiarism and procedures to be followed by students, little seems to have been mentioned on the academic consequences of practicing plagiarism at Euclid University. In several universities consequences of practicing plagiarism are made explicit to students and range from verbal cautions to termination of students from their academic study program. Doing so will definitely cultivate the culture of avoiding plagiarism during essay writing, increases academic honesty and originality in knowledge generation.

4) LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, the authors of coursepack1 described eleven reminders of "do's" and "don'ts" in writing literature review for academic papers. These include but not limited to:

- Use of comma to join two independent clauses, to bracket nonrestrictive phrases, and at the beginning of a sentence with an introductory clause or phrase.
- Not using comma to bracket phrases that give meaning to a sentence.
- Indicating possession and ending a singular noun with a sentence using an apostrophe that must be followed by an "s."
- Using appropriate punctuations to integrate quotations into sentences.
- Ensuring agreement between subjects and verbs.
- Proper use of pronouns, participial phrase and appositives in reference to a subject.
- Creating parallel sentence constructions and smooth flows.
- Using active voice as opposed to passive.
- Getting ride words that are of no value in a sentence (EUCLID 2019, 17–22).

In addition to the above 11 reminders in writing literature review, the authors also provided some English language rules that must be followed. These include:

- An apostrophe comes before "s" in any.
- Possessive singular noun and after "s" in any possessive plural noun. Only exception for this rule is the possessive form of "it" that is used without an apostrophe.
- "It's" means "it is" which is a contraction as opposed to "its", a possessive form of "it".
- The difference between "Your" and "You're" is that the earlier is a possessive form of "you" and the later means "you are" and must be used in that sense.
- The word "That" must only be used when it precedes a restrictive phrase and the word "which" used it precedes a non-restrictive phrase.
- A comma must be included to separate items listed in a sentence. It's also a must to include a comma before the word "and" that precedes the last item in the list.
- Numbers must be written as numerals, the only exception is when used at the beginning of a sentence or used as "second", "third", etc.
- The word "a" should precede a consonant and "an" precedes as a vowel.
- The difference between the words "good" and "well" is that "good" is only used as an adjective to modify a noun and "well" can either be used as an adverb or as an adjective. In certain circumstances the two words can used interchangeably but more often "well" is more affirmative than "good."
- A sentence can be started using "and" but only experienced writers might have the potential to make good use of it.
- The difference between "I" and "me" that the earlier is a subject pronoun and the latter is an object pronoun (EUCLID 2019, 17–22).

Although excellent explanation was made between commonly miss-used English Language words when writing a literature review, the focus on English language grammar and not the subject/discipline specific content of a literature review writing process dis-engages the heading of this chapter "literature review" from its content. This is because the elaborately discussed distinctions between prioritized words in this section of course park1 are not only used in writing literature review but also in routine write-ups for other purpose.

5) WRITING ACADEMIC PAPERS, SOME RULES OF THUMB

Some relevant rules and or suggestions have been described for writing academic papers. First, "PhD" students have been advised to use the opening paragraph of their academic paper to make explicit the main thesis. Secondly, they must stay focused by describing the important and relevant aspects of a theory or subject matter, by describing a particular question or problems they are trying to tackle in the paper by confining their argument on that specific question or problem. Thirdly, they must not create reader suspicion about what they say in writing by making concrete statements that generalize a concept to a given society or community when in reality it might not be true (Fallacy). Fourthly, students must focus the attention of the readers on ideas rather than words expressing the ideas. Fifthly, avoid clumsy and boring write-ups by using active sentence constructions, avoiding word repeat and unnecessary prepositional clauses. Sixth, supporting assertions by only quoting passages from the person whose ideas you are addressing play an important role in write-ups or when are differing ideas from the authors or writers. Seventh, taking views of other authors whose write-ups you read serious, and avoiding unsubstantiated criticism to other authors by assuming you have misinterpreted their write-ups and need to have deep reflection on their subject matter. Lastly proof-reading your paper by adopting the practice of reading it out loud as well as avoiding plagiarism by referencing sources of information (EUCLID 2019, 14–16).

6) STYLE GUIDE AND ITS NEED IN ACADEMIC WRITING

Writing style guides are basic rules that must be followed by writers. They are developed through collaborative processes by different writers in order to avoid imposition of an individual's writing style. They also appeal to the interest of the publishing company. Using one writing style is particularly important for companies with large number of authors because it ensures consistency and coherency in the final products of writing projects e.g. a book or research article (EUCLID 2019, 24–26).

In written English language, several writing styles exists and the possibility of agreeing upon a single, universally applied style remains uncertain because of arguments based on preferences of individual writers and publishing companies. These preferences emerged from several components of a written document such as; writing layouts, sentence length, spelling types, font sizes, use of abbreviations etc., as detailed in ACA-401D coursepack. However, certain elements in written English language are globally established among writers and publishing companies. These include correct grammar and punctuations among others (EUCLID 2019, 24–26)

Although a writing style may not be very important to freelance writers, demonstrating use of one established style and learning from customer feedback will add value to the writing output of freelance writers. The Economist style guide, BBC News style guide and the Chicago Manual of Style websites have been recommended by ACA-401D coursepack developers as good reference sources for learning more about established writing styles.

7) **CONCLUSION**

A good writer in English language must have excellent knowledge and skills in essay writing, avoid plagiarism, understand the do's and don'ts in writing literature review, know the rules of thumb for writing academic papers, and use appropriate English Language writing style.

REFERENCE

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd Ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University. Euclid University.

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